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Research Article

**RATE OF PREVALENCE OF HEPATOCELLULAR
CARCINOMA IN PATIENTS OF HCV INFECTION AFTER
DIRECT ANTIVIRAL TREATMENT**

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the rate of prevalence of HCC (Hepatocellular Carcinoma) in the patients suffering from HCV infection after getting treatment with DAA (Direct Acting Antiviral).

Methodology: This transverse research work was carried out in Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan from July 2018 to March 2020. We selected a sum of three hundred patients present with HCV genotype-3 with non-probability sampling method. All these patients were present with no past or current history of hepatocellular carcinoma. We gave the patients direct acting antiviral agents and followed these patients for complete six months after the completion of the treatment. Results were depending upon the quantitative PCR to evaluate the SVR (Sustained Virological Response) and ultrasound to examine the presence of any new abrasion. We presented the data in average, standard deviations, frequencies and percentages and we used the SPSS V.24 for the statistical analysis of collected information.

Results: Among three hundred patients, 59.70% (n: 179) patients were males and 40.30% (n: 121) patients were from female gender. The mean age of the patients was 55.080 ± 5.6020 years. There were 71.30% (n: 214) patients, present with the compensated cirrhosis at onset of treatment and 28.70% (n: 86) patients were present with decompensated cirrhosis. There was achievement of sustained virological response in 93.40% (n: 200) patients out of total 214 patients having compensated cirrhosis and 88.30% (n: 76) patients out of eighty-six were present with decompensated cirrhosis. After 6 months of treatment, 3.33% (n: 10) patients were present with the development of hepatocellular carcinoma, 0.70% (n: 2) patients in the compensated group and 2.70% (n: 8) patients present in decompensated group, out of these patients 6.60% (n: 5) patients achieved the sustained virological response.

Conclusion: The rate of prevalence of hepatocellular carcinoma after the treatment through direct acting antiviral agents is much significant (3.30%) even after the achievement of sustained virological RESPONSE. There must be exercise of caution in prescribing the direct acting antiviral agents to the patients of HCV infection, keeping the abnormality of hepatocellular carcinoma in minds.

KEYWORDS: Infection, Sustained Virological Response, Direct Acting Antiviral, Hepatocellular Carcinoma, Cirrhosis, Compensated, Decompensated, Onset, Prevalence.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatocellular carcinoma is one of the most important reasons of mortality from cancer in the whole world [1]. In USA, it has emerged as the fastest growing reason of death in the patients of cancer [2]. The availability of the liver cirrhosis has been attributed to developing the hepatocellular carcinoma [3]. Most leading contributors of the hepatocellular carcinoma are the chronic infections of HBV & HCV [4]. With the development of vaccine of HBV, an important decline in hepatocellular carcinoma related with HBV patients has been noticed [5] but the patients associated to HCV infections are on rise. In a patient suffering from HCV infection, it takes a mean duration of 20 to 30 years for the occurrence of cirrhosis, with hepatocellular carcinoma appearing in approximately 1.0% to 8.0% of the patients [6]. Some other factors having important association with the hepatocellular carcinoma risk include NAFLD (Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease) causing NASH (Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis) [7] in addition to the HCV-RNA viral load, gender, age of the patients, count of platelets and the fibrosis duration [8].

Availability and non-availability of the cirrhosis is most important contributory factor of the risk of hepatocellular carcinoma. In the patients of HCV infection who are present without cirrhosis but have achieved sustained virological response, there is very low risk for the development of hepatocellular carcinoma as compared to the patients of HCV infection with cirrhosis even after achievement of sustained virological response, there is still persistence of the risk for hepatocellular carcinoma. Although the prevalence of the HCV patients has shown a decrease in past few years but its occurrence in the patients present with hepatocellular carcinoma continues to increase [9]. Interferon treatment caused the improvement in severity of fibrosis and cirrhosis in the patients of HCV infection having liver complications [10]. There was inhibition in the utilization of the interferon to the patients present with compensated liver diseases.

Direct acting antiviral agents have transformed the administration of the HCV infection as well as it showed the high effectiveness in terms of attainment of sustained virological response in the patients of HCV [11, 12]. Different research works performed in the world have not stated the rate of prevalence of new patients of hepatocellular carcinoma but stated the hepatocellular carcinoma recurrence in the patients having infection of HCV. Some other research works have compared the hepatocellular carcinoma prevalence in the patients who obtained interferon-based treatment with those who were provided with direct acting antiviral agents. All

these research works showed a large variation in the marked results. There is very limited data present on our population demonstrating the rate of prevalence of hepatocellular carcinoma after the therapy with agents of direct acting antiviral in the patients present with HCV Genotype-3. The main rationale of this research work was to find out the rate of occurrence of hepatocellular carcinoma in HCV patients after treatment with direct acting antiviral agents.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work was carried out in Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan from July 2018 to March 2020. We recruited total 300 patients with non-probability purposive sampling method, keeping the confidence level as 95.0%, 3.0% error margin and taking the expected hepatocellular carcinoma percentage in the patients having treatment with direct acting antiviral agents as 3.20% [2]. All the patients with the history of hepatocellular carcinoma as evaluated by screening at the time of recruitment were included in this research work. The regimen of treatment for the patients contained direct acting antiviral comprising nucleotide analogue sofosbuvir 400.0 mg daily, NS5A-inhibitor daclatasvir 60.0 mg daily without or with the ribavirin 800.0 mg daily. We included only Child Pugh Class-A and Class-B in this research work. All the patients suffering from compensated cirrhosis i.e., Child Pugh Class-A were provided only sofosbuvir 400.0 mg in combination with daclatasvir 60.0 mg daily for a period of 12 weeks. All the patients present with decompensated cirrhosis i.e., Child Pugh Class-B were provided with a regimen of triple drug; sofosbuvir, daclatasvir & ribavirin for complete twenty-four weeks. We performed the CBC (Complete Blood Counts), test for liver functions, PT (Prothrombin Time), INR (International Normalized Ratio), abdomen ultrasound, AFP (Alpha Fetoprotein), ELISA for anti-HCV followed by the quantitative PCR to identify the genotyping of HCV and viral load. We performed most of the tests on monthly basis on whole duration of treatment. The most common genotype in the population of our country Pakistan is Genotype-3, so we recruited only the patients of Genotype-3.

We excluded the patients who were present with abrasions on liver or other coinfections of HCV and HCV. We did not include the patients having less than eighteen or greater than seventy years of age. We also excluded the females with pregnancy, patients with fragile health and patients present with mental illnesses.

We performed the quantitative PCR at the end of therapy with the direct acting antiviral and then after three months of completion of treatment to evaluate the Sustained Virological Response. Any suspicious

abrasion of liver after or during the treatment, as identified on the ultrasound of abdomen was further confirmed by the levels of serum AFP. We used the SPSS V.23 for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We calculated and presented the quantitative data as weight, height, age and body mass index in averages and standard deviations. We presented the qualitative data as gender, availability or non-presence on hepatocellular carcinoma in forms of percentages and frequencies.

RESULTS:

Three hundred patients were the participants of this research work, out of them 59.70% (n: 179) patients were males and 40.30% (n: 121) patients were females. Average age of the patients was 55.080 ± 5.620 years. Out of 179 males, 74.30% (n: 133) were present with compensated cirrhosis at start of therapy with direct acting antiviral agents and 25.60% (n: 46) patients were present with decompensated cirrhosis. Likewise, 67.0% (n: 81) out of 121 females who got recruitment in this research work were present with compensated cirrhosis and 33.0% (n: 40) females were present with decompensated cirrhosis.

Table-I: Frequency Distribution of All Variables

Variables	Male		Female		Average / Total	
	No / Mean	Percent / SD	No / Mean	Percent / SD	No / Mean	Percent / SD
Age	53.89	5.56	56.83	5.2	55.08	5.62
Sex	179	59.7	121	40.3	300	100
Child-Pugh class A	133	62.1	81	37.9	214	71.3
Child-Pugh class B	46	53.5	40	46.5	86	28.7
Sustained Virological Response Achieved	163	59	113	41	276	92
Sustained Virological Response not achieved	16	66.6	8	33.3	24	8
No Hepatocellular Carcinoma	173	59.7	117	40.3	290	96.7
Hepatocellular Carcinoma	6	60	4	40	10	3.3

There was achievement of sustained virological response in 93.40% (n: 200) out of 214 patients having compensated cirrhosis, of which 61.50% (n: 123) patients were men and 38.50% (n: 77) patients were females and in 88.30% (n: 76) out of 86 patients present with decompensated cirrhosis, 52.60% (n: 40) were male patients and 47.40% (n: 36) were female patients. We followed these patients for other three months after the examination of the sustained virological response status.

Table-II: Sustained Virological Response and Hepatocellular Carcinoma in Child Pugh Class A and B

Outcome	Child Pugh A (Compensated cirrhosis) n=214			Child Pugh B (Decompensated cirrhosis) n=86		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Sustained Virological Response achieved	123	77	200(93.4%)	40	36	76(88.4%)
Hepatocellular Carcinoma in Sustained Virological Response achieved group	0	0	0	3	2	5(6.6%)
Sustained Virological Response not achieved	10	4	14(6.6%)	6	4	10(11.6%)
Hepatocellular Carcinoma in Sustained Virological Response not achieved group	2	0	2(14.3%)	2	1	3(30%)
Total Hepatocellular Carcinoma	2	0	2(14.3%)	5	3	8(9.3%)
No Hepatocellular Carcinoma	131	81	212(99%)	42	36	78(90.7%)

In the patients of compensated group, 14.30% (n: 2) out of fourteen patients who did not achieve the Sustained Virological Response developed hepatocellular carcinoma at 6 months after the treatment. No patient of the compensated group who achieved sustained virological response was present with development of hepatocellular carcinoma. In the decompensated group, 9.30% (n: 8) out of eighty-six patients developed hepatocellular carcinoma, out of which 6.60% (n: 5) out of seventy-six patients were present with achieved sustained virological

response and 30.0% (n: 3) patients out of ten were present with not-achieved sustained virological response. From total ten patients who were present with development of hepatocellular carcinoma, 60.0% (n: 6) patients were males and 40.0% (n: 4) patients were females. So, this current research work showed a significant percentage of the patients who were present with development of hepatocellular carcinoma as ten out of three hundred patients (3.30%) following the therapy with agents of direct acting antiviral for the infection of HCV Genotype-3.

DISCUSSION:

HCV Genotype-3 is 2nd most prevalent genotype of HCV in the world influencing about 54.30 million population that account for 30.10% [13]. Research work conducted in last few years cited that there is association of HCV Genotype-3 with the rise in the progression of cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. In one other research work conducted in Sweden, stated different risk factors which can exaggerate the progression of liver fibrosis are male gender [OR= 1.6 (95.0% CI= 1.210-2.120), P <0.0010], Genotype-3 infection [OR= 1.890 (1.370-2.610), P <0.0010], histological activity [OR=2.030 (1.540-2.680), P< 0.0010] and age at the time of infection [OR= 1.080 (1.060-1.090), P< 0.0010] [14]. In a French research work, 34.0% rate of occurrence of hepatocellular carcinoma was reported after five years in the patients suffering from HCV infection of Genotype-3 associated cirrhosis [15].

One other research work conducted L Renaldi on 280 patients treated in four different centers of Southern part of Italy. The patient's follow-up in the initial months of treatment reported the high sustained virological response rate (97.10%). However, they found 9 new patients of hepatocellular carcinoma in initial weeks following the treatment with a prevalence of 3.20%. About fifty percent patients of hepatocellular carcinoma appeared at the end of the antiviral treatment [3].

Fasiha Kanwal in his research work stated that calculated hepatocellular carcinoma risk in the patients of cirrhosis was 4.70 times higher as compared to the non-cirrhotic patients (adjusted HR=4.730, 95.0% CI, 3.340-6.680) [16]. Conti in his research work conducted on 344 patients of cirrhosis, out of which there was previously presence of hepatocellular carcinoma in 59 patients and 285 patients did not have hepatocellular carcinoma. They followed the patients for 24 weeks. Out of 59 patients with previously hepatocellular carcinoma, there was recurrence in seventeen whereas 9 out of 285 patients developed hepatocellular carcinoma who were tumor free in past [17]. One other research work conducted by Reig M on one hundred and three patients successfully got treatment for hepatocellular carcinoma and they were provided with direct acting antiviral agents for the infections of HCV. That research work followed the only 58 patients who fulfilled the inclusion standard of study. The median duration of the follow up was 5.70 months. There

was occurrence of mortality in 3 patients and there was recurrence of tumor in sixteen patients [18].

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this research work concluded that in decompensated group, even after achievement of sustained virological response, there was development of hepatocellular carcinoma in significant proportion of patients (6.60%). This research work was carried out on three hundred patients only in a single medical center, there is need of large trials involving multi-centers of different regions to consolidate the findings of this research work.

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